

CoARA Action Plan

2026-2030

March 2026

Kempelen Institute of Intelligent Technologies

Kempelen Institute of Intelligent Technologies (KInIT) is an independent institute focused on researching intelligent technologies including artificial intelligence (AI) and diverse areas of computer science, while also addressing the ethical dimensions of information technologies. Founded in 2020, KInIT conducts excellent research in the topics of web & user data processing, green and secure environment, natural language processing, ethics and human values in technology. The institute also aims at long-term industry collaborations and international partnerships, building an innovative ecosystem, and offers a PhD programme in cooperation with Brno University of Technology and the Faculty of Law, Palacký University in Olomouc in the Czech Republic.

KInIT contributes to recent paradigm shifts and initiatives currently being implemented in Slovakia. Previously, under *Comprehensive Accreditation* (last one being [KA 2016](#)), Slovak universities and research institutions were predominantly assessed using standard bibliometric indicators such as Journal Impact Factor (JIF), h-index, citation counts, and publication counts in indexed journals. Contrastingly, the new evaluation *Periodic Evaluation of Research, Development, Artistic and Other Creative Activities or Verification of Excellence in Research 2022* ([VER 2022](#)) introduced international peer review panels which assessed the quality, originality, and international visibility of research and art outputs, supplemented by bibliometric data only as contextual information. Even though KInIT, as an independent institution, has not yet been officially included in the national evaluations VER 2022 and [VER 2026](#), which are binding for public organization in Slovakia, our internal regulations are fully aligned, and we are committed to take actions to be a part of future assessments in a same way as these organizations.

The culture of continuous improvement in KInIT is also demonstrated by the *Human Resources Strategy for Researchers* (HRS4R) award, which KInIT acquired in January 2025 as the first non-university institution in Slovakia. HRS4R is a premier European Commission initiative which helps research institutions improve working conditions, recruitment practices and career development for researchers, gender equality and open science, while aligning with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers.

KInIT values diverse backgrounds and career trajectories, and our evaluation processes recognize the variety of roles and expertise across both our research and operations teams. This diversity is intentionally reflected in how diverse contributions are evaluated, ensuring that different forms of knowledge, skills, and career development are acknowledged and supported.

Hand in hand with the setting of a new Institute Research and Innovation Strategy and constituting Advisory Board of the Institute, in September 2025, KInIT has joined the *Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment* (CoARA) as a signatory, affirming its support for the ten core commitments that guide the reform of research assessment and dedication to implement measures outlined in the *Agreement for Reforming Research Assessment* (ARRA). This document presents the initial action plan for the years 2026-2030, outlining the steps KInIT will take to align its internal practices with CoARA principles and contribute to the broader transformation of research assessment.

Action plan for 2026-2030

The Commitments

1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

Established Practices

- KInIT recognizes diversity in research careers (“career pathing”) and consequently, of career progressions. As the independent research institute it welcomes diverse backgrounds of the staff including different fields (e.g., computer science, engineering, information science, philosophy, law, physics). Among the institute teams, different career paths are offered, reflecting research, engineering, or management tracks.
- KInIT has implemented researcher assessment criteria which are not limited to standard publication metrics, but include a broad spectrum of research outputs such as datasets, software, workflows, protocols, prototypes, intellectual property rights, standards, editorships, technical reports or innovations. Across these categories, the primary focus is on evaluating the societal impact of the outputs.
- Other activities are also considered valuable, including communication and dissemination tasks such as knowledge transfer, training and mentoring of researchers, public engagement actions, actions that contribute to a positive research culture and engagement with quadruple helix stakeholders, i.e, government, industry, academia, society.
- Employees are encouraged to produce non-refereed academic outputs, such as blog posts, popularization articles or social media posts. In these cases, the impact can be measured by tracking alternative metrics such as retweets, likes, web-page views, downloads, podcast listens, event audience numbers, social bookmarks, comments, or ratings.

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C1.1 KInIT will introduce systematic tracking of the societal impacts of its projects (e.g., political, health, technological, economic, legal, cultural, social, environmental, and others). This impact assessment will be required not only for final outputs, but also from the earliest stages of project consideration and throughout the project’s implementation. The individual researchers will be asked to identify the impact of their activities via a regular yearly evaluation process.
- C1.2 KInIT will upgrade the tracking process and system for conferences attendance tracking.
- C1.3 Hand in hand with HRS4R certification, different career paths will be regularly evaluated and updated, driven by the team leads and HR.

2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

Established Practices

- KInIT has already implemented alternative assessment criteria and processes. The quantitative bibliometric data are collected, but analyzed only on the level of the whole institute or research teams, not on a personal level. Tracking institute-level metrics is required by the institute's legal structure as well as by various national authorities.
- Even though some standard quantitative indicators will continue being collected (such as numbers of publications or citations, etc.), these statistics have no direct effect on employee or team performance evaluations or salary.
- Research teams performance evaluations are peer reviewed (evaluation panel consisting of institute directors - CEO, COO, CRO, CHRO) and based largely on self-assessment, considering diverse contributions and impacts with a focus more on the whole team rather than on individuals.
- Yearly evaluation criteria of researchers and PhD. students are structurally similar to the ones for non-researchers, focused more on results and impacts and on meeting personally designed achievements set for each year and future goals than on general and universal rules.

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C2.1 KInIT will implement a yearly research team evaluation realised through impact cases, in order to accentuate various societal impacts (i.e., political, health, technological, economic, legal, cultural, social, environmental) of their activities and to promote a culture of impact driven thinking about the outcomes beyond the scope of simple metrics. A template form for the evaluation will be prepared attached with respect to the nationwide assessment and best-practices abroad.
- C2.2 Quantitative indicators for individual researcher evaluation will be re-evaluated with the aim to minimise the amount.
- C2.3 Institute Advisory Board will be established to implement regular evaluations of the entire institute by a selection of external international experts.
- C2.4 KInIT will systematically advocate for including independent research organizations (incl. itself) to the national Periodic Evaluation. Aiming at this goal, internal processes will be introduced to eliminate unnecessary administrative load. Activity is not intended to add another layer of assessment, but as an act of expressing an official agreement with the initiatives towards more fair and qualitative evaluation and reform of R&I ecosystem.

3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.

Established Practices

- The pre-selection of the journals and venues suitable for the research team's publications is primarily guided by the quality assessment of CRO, with journal indicators and publication-based metrics being used only as an underlying information about the size of the field/area and to ensure we choose the most suitable ones. The overall initiative is to attend leading conferences, journals and events where key authorities in that field meet and to publish in the most peer-recognized journals within the specific research field. The institute recognizes different impacts and benefits, e.g., meeting of specific thematic oriented communities on a national or local level is also considered as valuable even though they have lower international scientific value, or in newly established events and conferences of recognized experts.
- During the regular annual evaluation, the evaluated individuals may or may not include indicators, citations, and other relevant metrics in the appropriate sections of the self-evaluation report and the specific relevance of these indicators to their respective research fields is acknowledged.

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C3.1 KInIT will continue to promote responsible use of bibliometric indicators, merely as a tool to support qualitative evaluation, placing greater emphasis on the role of peer review even when evaluating bibliometric indicators.
- C3.2 Institute will continually raise awareness of venue quality in the context of possibly predatory and unethical practices via different means, e.g., team research seminars, newsletters.

4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Established Practices

- Reflecting the independence of a research institute, the institutional assessment of KInIT does not depend on global or national university rankings as a measure of quality or performance, but rather on the internally determined factors.
- A balanced set of indicators are being used (e.g., open science practices, collaboration, interdisciplinarity, societal engagement) instead of rank-based metrics.

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C4.1 The Institute will promote the inclusion of itself and other independent research institutes in national external research evaluation, ensuring that all research organizations in Slovakia can be assessed under the same conditions as public institutions. This will further promote fair and qualitative assessment in the R&I ecosystem and raise awareness among relevant stakeholders.
- C4.2 KInIT's Advisory Board will be aligned with the assessment practices that move away from organisational rankings and instead foster a culture focused on continuous improvement and meaningful research quality
- C4.3 Institute will use benchmarking against self-defined goals or practices of peer institutions rather than rank tables, where comparison is needed.

5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to

Established Practices

- KInIT systematically advocates the importance of qualitative peer reviewed assessment on the national level.
- Personal resources were committed to creating a core team within KInIT, responsible for preparing this action plan and coordinating all planned activities.
- KInIT participated in several meetings with other Slovak institutions joining CoARA articulating the need for the transition toward impact driven outputs.

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C5.1 Resources will be allocated towards establishing an Advisory Board, in charge of producing an independent evaluation report on the main strengths and weaknesses as well as plans for further improvement.
- C5.2 KInIT will progress from being a CoARA signatory to a CoARA member in order to enable our future participation in National chapters or Working groups.
- C5.3 Further personal resources will be dedicated for the internal work needed to review and develop improved research assessment criteria, tools and processes. Beyond core team, two working groups will be established:
 - WG1 (executive component) - Researchers (junior/PhD, medior, senior), Research engineer (senior), grant management office representative
 - WG2 - (managerial component) - Team leads, CEO, CHRO.

- C5.4 KInIT will establish a feedback collection and set up regular evaluation cycles. First evaluation will be coordinated with the creation of the Advisory Board and with the planned participation in the VER 2030 national evaluation.
- C5.5 KInIT will actively engage in national CoARA activities and continue efforts toward the implementation of qualitative assessment frameworks for science and research in Slovakia.

6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes

Established Practices

- KInIT continues reviewing and updating research assessment criteria, tools and processes to ensure that these are in line with the Agreement for Reforming Research Assessment principles and commitments.
- KInIT contributes actively in the review of the national evaluation of science and research.
- Leading personnel at KInIT have previously participated in, and continue to be involved with, evaluation bodies and organizations in Slovakia (e.g. prof. Maria Bielikova was a former member of the Slovak Accreditation Committee, assoc. prof. Michal Kompan is currently a member of the Evaluation body of the Central register of publication activity records).
- Transparent evaluation frameworks and structured career pathing are being implemented within the institute (e.g., HRS4R).

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C6.1 KInIT will actively participate and endorse various national working groups formed at both the national and international levels. Various stakeholders will be actively involved in the preparatory phase of the evaluation, discussion on the evaluation concept and the collection of initial feedback.
- C6.2 KInIT will continue to be active in policy advocacy towards research evaluation transition.
- C6.3 KInIT will regularly communicate and raise awareness of the topic to the general public.

7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Established Practices

- The information about the research assessment reform and our internal regulations in this regard are communicated, but predominantly to the newly joined researchers and PhD students as a part of their introductory training materials.

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C7.1 Regular internal seminars will be prepared and organized for each research team as well as more comprehensive onboarding materials for newcomers to raise awareness.
- C7.2 A dedicated web page will be created on the institutional web, providing further information about the CoARA membership.
- C7.3 Additional awareness-raising initiatives will be realised including communication on the topic of research assessment reform on national or international panels, fairs, venues and communicating benefits to national authorities.
- C7.4 KInIT will act as a role-model for other national research institutions.

8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

Established Practices

- KInIT participates in meetings and working groups in order to allow exchanging practices and experiences and enable mutual learning.
- The topic of research assessment is regularly discussed with our international partners.

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C8.1 KInIT will utilize existing networks and international project consortia to exchange good practices not only within the Coalition, but also with the international partners which have similar values and evaluation systems.
- C8.2 KInIT will participate in regular meetings with other Slovak institutions joining CoARA.
- C8.3 KInIT is committed to enhance its international network, promoting collaborations and exchanges with other research evaluation agencies, within and beyond the Coalition.
- C8.4 KInIT will continue to monitor developments within CoARA, including the topics discussed and other relevant activities.

9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C9.1 This Action Plan will be published on Zenodo in accordance with CoARA customs and then on the KInIT website in order to raise awareness of the KInIT's commitment to the adherence to CoARA principles and to the implementation of CoARA recommendations.

- C9.2 Institute internal meetings involving all relevant employees informing them about our commitments, planned changes and their progress will be organised.
- C9.3 KInIT will yearly review and evaluate the progress made with this Action Plan on the yearly basis.
- C9.4 Achievements and progress can also be communicated in the form of social media or blog posts.

10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

Established Practices

- KInIT regularly participates in major international scientific conferences worldwide, allows researchers to stay updated on the state-of-the-art of research in the field and exchange relevant practices, including the topic of research assessment reform, regular practices and ongoing improvements happening in other countries and institutions.
- KInIT's holistic open science policy already covers the key topics of open access to publications, research data, source code, public licences and citizen science. The researchers are encouraged to follow the FAIR principles, making data and outputs as open as possible by default (unless prevented by commercial agreements), and to benefit from initiatives such as the AI-on-Demand Platform, OpenAIRE, Zenodo, EOSC, and OSF, which promote early and open sharing of research and reproducibility.

Strategic Priorities Ahead

- C10.1 Knowledge generated during the research assessment reform will be made available for evidence gathering and research on research.
- C10.2 KInIT will provide access to the list of publication outputs and case studies evaluated in the context of the periodical national research assessment exercise, providing open access to the full text when available, to facilitate evidence gathering and research.
- C10.3 A summary of the evaluation, including general outcomes, will be made publicly available on our website. This will provide transparent access and inspiration for any interested stakeholders.

Timeline of individual activities

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